

Early Versus Delayed Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy for Acute Cholecystitis a Prospective Randomized Controlled Trial

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Abstract

Background: Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy is not proven for acute Cholecystitis till now. This prospective randomized study aimed to compare and assess laparoscopic cholecystectomy protection & viability for acute & delayed cholecystectomy consequences. **Methods:** A total of 40 patients with severe Cholecystitis were assigned to one of two groups: early laparoscopic Cholecystectomy within 24 hours of admission (early group, n =20) or conservative treatment accompanied by delayed cholecystectomy (late group, n = 20).(delayed community, n =20) 6–12 weeks after Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy **Results:** There were no significant differences in alteration rates (early 5.3 days versus delayed 4.8 days), Postoperative complications (early 5.3 days versus delayed 4.8 days), or postoperative time differences (early 104 minutes versus delayed 4.8 days) (early, 15 percent vs. delayed, 20 percent). On the other hand, the primary group had slightly extra blood loss (228 versus 114 ml) and spent less time in the hospital (4.1 vs. 10.1 days). **Conclusion:** Early Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy for severe Cholecystitis is protective & viable, with the extra advantage of lesser hospitalizations. Patients with acute Cholecystitis should be made available if surgery is carried out 72 to 96 hours after symptoms are started.

Keywords: acute Cholecystitis, Cholecystectomy, laparoscopy,

Introduction

The gold standard for treatment of patients with symptomatic gallstones is laparoscopic Cholecystectomy.(1) During its early stages of development, severe Cholecystitis was considered a contraindication to Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. Some centers focused on using laparoscopy

in acute Cholecystitis as laparoscopy becomes more standard procedure. (1-3) this means it is practically feasible as well as safe. On the other hand, the conversion rate is relatively high. Early open Cholecystectomy was better than delaying open Cholecystectomy in the manner of hospital stays in some randomized trials. Still, both had comparable mortality and morbidity in the days before laparoscopic surgery. (4-7). Early Cholecystitis surgery has grown in popularity since the late 1980s. Early recovery and shorter hospital stay are connected to successful laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. However, the potential of severe complications can outweigh the benefits of early Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. (8) A high rate of conversion. Theoretically, a more safe procedure at lower rates of conversion may result in conservative antibiotic treatment preceded by Cholecystectomy six to eight weeks later, following a decrease of acute inflammation. A lack of prospective data to compare the option between the two treatment methods is difficult. There have only been two randomized trials (9)(10, 11) reported. We performed randomized observational trials to equate early and delayed Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy to treat severe Cholecystitis.

Methodology

Patient selection and study design

The Hospital Ethics Committee approved this report. The study included 40 patients admitted to the Department of Surgery with acute Cholecystitis. A combination of clinical and ultrasonography criteria was diagnosed with acute Cholecystitis (coated, distended edematous; positive Murphy sign; apparent gallstone & Pericholecystic fluid assortment). A hepatobiliary iminodiacetic acid ⁹⁹Tc scan was performed in ambiguous situation patients with indications. More than 96 hours, earlier abdominal operation, co-occurrence common bile duct, or a severe condition interpreting the Patients not eligible for Laparoscopic procedure were omitted from the study. The study included the decision was made to seek informed permission. Then one of two groups: "early" or "delayed," were assigned to patients. Randomization was carried out by a computer-generated list of numbers kept by a third party. Within 24 hours of the randomization, Intravenous fluids & Antibiotics, like Ampicillin, Gentamicin, & Metronidazole, have been treated in an early group with laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. Following the subsiding of the acute episode, a choice of laparoscopic Cholecystectomy offered for patients referred to

conservation care 6 to 12 weeks later. An emergency open cholecystectomies were performed in patients not responding to conservative therapy.

Table 1. Clinical data and laboratory results for the patients in the early and delayed groups at admission

	Early group (n = 20)	Delayed group (n = 20)	p Value
Age (years)	41.5 ± 11.4	38.6 ± 11.4	0.435
Sex (M:F)	3:17	5:15	0.542
Previous lower abdominal surgery	4	4	0.433
Previous biliary symptoms	3	2	0.546
Duration of acute symptoms (h)	35.1 ± 19.1	36.1 ± 24.7	0.887
Duration of symptoms > 3 days	2	5	0.329
Maximum temperature (°F)	99.7 ± 0.2	99.2 ± 0.1	0.712
Total leukocyte count (> 11,000/ml)	13	11	0.192
Total bilirubin (mg%)	0.7 ± 0.13	0.6 ± 0.14	0.391
Aspartate transaminase (U/l)	40.7 ± 20	30.8 ± 14	0.096
Alanine transaminase (U/l)	35.3 ± 18	25.4 ± 13	0.065
Alkaline phosphatase (IU/l)	187 ± 68	153 ± 48	0.072

Table 2. Ultrasound findings for the patients

Ultrasound findings (U/S)	Early group (n = 20) n (%)	Delayed group (n = 20) n (%)	p Value
Thickened edematous gallbladder	12 (60)	11 (55)	0.536
Distended gallbladder	17 (85)	15 (75)	0.901
Presence of gallstones	20 (100)	20 (100)	0.890
U/S Murphy's sign positive	11 (55)	13 (65)	0.769
Pericholecystic fluid	03 (15)	03 (15)	0.543

Surgical process

Surgeons did the procedure under general anesthesia & endotracheal intubation. With the help of open Hasson technique, pneumoperitoneum was determined.

The laparoscopic procedure was performed using two 10 mm ports (one 10 mm infra-umbilical cord for optical, one epigastric for dissector/ sugar) and two of 5 mm ports (1 along the margin of subcostal along with the right hypochondria, in the Right side). A 5th port was added if necessary to increase visibility. The first step was to release the adhesion and expose Calot's triangle. The gallbladder was drained if needed via a suction needle to permit improved gripping. The cystic pedicle was dissected to differentiate between the cystic duct and the artery. They were clipped off and separated afterward. During the procedure, a cholangiogram was not done. A monopolar cautery hook dissected the gall bladder. The gall bladder was put in the endo bag and discarded with the epigastric incision, which would be extended, if possible when the operation was completed. Homeostasis has been achieved in the gallbladder bed, and a suction drain is positioned.

Study parameters

All patient Demographics, functioning results, alteration into an open choice, reasons for alteration, time of operation, analgesic requirements after the procedure, pain score after the process (VAS score), hospital stay after the operation, total hospitalization (including admission and admission to the delayed surgical group) were collected.

Statistical analysis

In the statistical review, the chi-square test & paired t-test were used. The p-value of less than 0.05 was defined as significant.

Results

Forty patients were randomized: 20 early & 20 delays during the research. Both groups were well-balanced in age and gender and clinical and lab criteria. No patient in the delayed community needed emergency operation due to lack of conventional care or repeated indications after discharge. After the first admission, an average interval of 68 days was performed with delayed laparoscopic Cholecystectomy (range, 48–140 days).

Table 3. Modification of the operative technique

Modification of the technique	Early group (<i>n</i> = 20) <i>n</i> (%)	Delayed group (<i>n</i> = 20) <i>n</i> (%)	<i>p</i> Value
Gallbladder decompression	16 (80)	1 (5)	0.001
Retrieval bag	7 (35)	0	0.012
Subhepatic drain	16 (80)	7 (35)	0.023
Use of a fifth port	02 (10)	0	0.456
Enlargement of the epigastric port site	1 (5)	1 (5)	0.321

Operative time and procedures

More operational procedures were needed by the early group & extended time than the late group. The average time of the early group was 104 minutes (range: 40-210 minutes), and the average time of operation for the late group was 93 (range: 35-200 minutes). Statistically significant was not the difference in operation time ($p = 0.433$). In the Laparoscopic active group, the actual working time was 87 minutes at the beginning of the group, compared with 80 minutes at the late group ($p=0.671$). On average, the early group lost 228 mL, and 114 mL ($p=0,006$) was lost in the delayed group. A blood transfusion was not necessary for either party.

Conversion to open surgery

In the early group, five patients (25%) and the late group, five (25%), were undergoing an open operation (conversion) ($p=0.540$). In the first case of transformation, the main technical reasons were the ambiguous anatomy of the Calot's triangle, suspicion of injury to the bile duct, milder injury to the bile duct, and transection of the gallbladder. Dense adherences to Calot's triangle made the dissection in the delayed category difficult, contributing to the change.

Postoperative pain score and analgesic requirement

The early group required 5.3 days of postoperative analgesics, while the delayed group needed 4.8 days. On the first postoperative day, the VAS pain score was slightly different, but not on the second or third days.

Hospital stay

In the early groups, the median total hospital stay was 4.1 days for the early group (range: 2-20 days), while the late group averaged 10.1 days (range: 5-23 days) for the total hospital stay ($p=0.023$). The early group had 3.2 days (range, 1–20 days) of the mean postoperative hospital stay, and the delayed group was 2.3 days (range, 1–7 days) ($p = .952$).

Table 4: overall comparison between early and delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy group

S. no.		Early group (n = 20)	Delayed group (n = 20)	p Value
1	Age (years)	41.5 ± 11.4	38.6 ± 11.4	0.435
2	Sex (M:F)	3:17	5:15	
3	Duration of symptoms (hours)	35.1 ± 19.1	36.1 ± 24.7	0.887
4	Operating time (min)	104.3 ± 44	93 ± 45	0.433
5	Blood loss (ml)	228.5 ± 142	114.5 ± 99	0.006
6	Postoperative stay (days)	3.2 ± 8	2.3 ± 2	0.161
7	Total hospital stay (days)	4.1 ± 8.6	10.1 ± 6.1	0.023
8	Postoperative analgesia (days)	5.3 ± 1.4	4.8 ± 0.7	0.182
9	Conversion rate	25%	25%	0.540
10	Complications	4 (20%)	3 (15%)	0.456

Discussion

Severe Cholecystitis was treated in a comparative contradiction with laparoscopic Cholecystectomy in the first year after laparoscopic surgery. Recently, Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy has been exposed to be possible and safe in acute Cholecystitis. High alteration

rates of 6 (35%) have been stated in various studies. (12, 13) Early laparoscopic cholecystectomy was used to treat severe Cholecystitis. (14)(15)

This research shows the general assumption that the chances of good Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy at a later time are improved with the initial conservative care is false. Early as well as late groups had similar conversion rates in our sample. On the other hand, the motives for conversion were quite different. When the flaky and odd gallbladder was caught in the early group, it tore. In addition, a lot of oozing occurred due to acute inflammation. These are problems that we find difficult to address at first. The anatomy of the Calot triangle, except for one instance, was relatively straightforward. Therefore, the conversion rate decreased with early community experience (60 percent in the first 5 cases to 13 percent in the last 15 cases). Thick adhesions, which obscure the anatomy of the Calot triangle, were the primary explanation for the change to a delayed community. We rely on that more practice with early surgery will lower conversion rates in these cases.

Bile duct damage is probably the most severe problem when comparing the two classes. None of the patients had delayed bile duct damage. However, significant leakage of the gallbladder occurred in the early community. In one patient the anatomy of Calot's triangle was unclear at laparoscopy. After the surgery, an intra-operational cholangiogram was carried out. There was a wide and short cystic duct. The stump of the cystic duct was closed with interrupted Vicryl ligatures.

At the intersection of the cystic duct-common bile duct, pinhole rent was made in another patient while the Hartmann pouch was traced. During the laparoscopic procedure, this was detected. It was tenting to suture it laparoscopically, but because of the brittle nature of the tissues, we decided against this. The procedure turned to open surgery, and a small 4-0 Vicryl suture closed the small hole. This course was given after randomized surgery. Therefore, in the early group, there was a significant complexity.

Maximum surgeons consider the operation time to be critical for determining the result. The procedure should be performed immediately after acceptance. While operating within the "golden 72 hours" of the initiation of symptoms has been recommended. (16), given the logistical challenges of operating in emergencies for these patients, early operation in clinical practices is not always practical. According to the next optional operating list, early group

patients were operated on. As a result, within 24 hours after admission, 90% of our patients received surgery. (17)

Early surgery results determine the technical challenge of laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. A relaxed edematous gallbladder comprising contaminated bile is typical in acute cholecystitis cases. We conclude from our experience that many scientific vital points must be considered when conducting laparoscopic surgery for acute cholecystitis. The gall bladder should be decompressed in advance for a good view of Calot's triangle since this makes the gall bladder easier to grab and retract.

Our findings reinforce the theory that the swelling of acute cholecystitis produces an edema plane around the gall bladder, making separation from the structures around them more accessible. The inflamed gallbladder is waiting to cool, causing the surrounding inflammation to mature and organization, making it more difficult to disintegrate. In addition, although the triangle of Calot may not be involved in early inflammation, chronic inflammatory scars distort the triangle of Calot, thereby making dissection more difficult in this crucial area. Both groups had similar pain ratings and analgesic criteria after surgery. Although patients from the early group needed more extended operations than delayed patients. However, the average stay in the hospital for the delayed group was slightly longer as in the early group.

Conclusion

Finally, early Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy is viable & effective for acute cholecystitis. We assume that the incidence of complications in the early group decreases as the surgeon's experience increases. Delays in laparoscopic Cholecystectomy cannot lower than the conversion rate linked with Early Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. The early laparoscopic operation provides permanent treatment at admission, evades complications with unsuccessful caution & repeated emergency surgery symptoms. Early functions are also connected with a significantly shorter hospitalization, which considerably saves the patient and the healthcare system.

References

1. Wu X-D, Tian X, Liu M-M, Wu L, Zhao S, Zhao LJJoBS. Meta-analysis comparing early versus delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis. 2015;102(11):1302-13.
2. Cox M, Wilson T, Luck A, Jeans P, Padbury R, Toouli JJAos. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute inflammation of the gallbladder. 1993;218(5):630.

3. Lyu Y, Cheng Y, Wang B, Zhao S, Chen LJSe. Early versus delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis: an up-to-date meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. 2018;32(12):4728-41.
4. Järvinen HJ, Hästbacka JJAos. Early cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis: a prospective randomized study. 1980;191(4):501.
5. Lahtinen J, Alhava E, Aukee SJSjog. Acute cholecystitis treated by early and delayed surgery. A controlled clinical trial. 1978;13(6):673-8.
6. McArthur P, Cuschieri A, Sells R, Shields RJJoBS. Controlled clinical trial comparing early with interval cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis. 1975;62(10):850-2.
7. Khalid S, Iqbal Z, Bhatti AAJJoAMC, Abbottabad: JAMC. Early Versus Delayed Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy For Acute Cholecystitis. 2017;29(4):570-3.
8. Zafar SN, Obirieze A, Adesibikan B, Cornwell EE, Fullum TM, Tran DDJJs. Optimal time for early laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis. 2015;150(2):129-36.
9. Agrawal R, Sood K, Agarwal BJSr, practice. Evaluation of early versus delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy in acute cholecystitis. 2015;2015.
10. Lai P, Kwong K, Leung K, Kwok S, Wchan A, Chung S, et al. Randomized trial of early versus delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis. 1998;85(6):764-7.
11. Lo C-M, Liu C-L, Fan S-T, Lai E, Wong JJAos. Prospective randomized study of early versus delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis. 1998;227(4):461.
12. Miller RE, Kimmelstiel FMJSe. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis. 1993;7(4):296-9.
13. Cao AM, Eslick GD, Cox MRJJoGS. Early cholecystectomy is superior to delayed cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis: a meta-analysis. 2015;19(5):848-57.
14. Wiesen SM, Unger SW, Barkin JS, Edelman DS, Scott JSJTAjog. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy: the procedure of choice for acute cholecystitis. 1993;88(3):334-7.
15. Thangavelu A, Rosenbaum S, Thangavelu DJTJoem. Timing of cholecystectomy in acute cholecystitis. 2018;54(6):892-7.
16. Bagla P, Sarria JC, Riall TSJCoiid. Management of acute cholecystitis. 2016;29(5):508-13.
17. Maehira H, Kawasaki M, Itoh A, Ogawa M, Mizumura N, Toyoda S, et al. Prediction of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis. 2017;216:143-8.